

USE OF NUMBERS TO INCREASE STUDENT AUTONOMY

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Abstract: *In modern education researchers reveal their interest in finding the optimal way to improve students' learning process. Since the teaching paradigm shifted from teacher-centered to student-centered, many solutions have been proposed to make learning motivating and inspiring. This led researchers to conclude that motivation comes primarily from within, thus making students responsible for their own knowledge. This article discusses the advantages and challenges of autonomous education. It focuses on the importance of developing autonomy in students who can fully control their learning process.*

Keywords: *modern education, learner autonomy, student-centeredness, CALL, learning style, full control.*

Introduction: The modern tendencies in EFL reveal the researchers' interest in finding the optimal way of enhancing the students' learning process. Since the shift in the teaching paradigm from teacher-centeredness to student-centeredness, many solutions have been offered to make learning motivational and inspiring. This led the researchers to the conclusion that motivation should first of all come from within, thus, making the students responsible for their own learning. It goes without saying that the teacher still holds an important role in the students' academic development. The human factor is essential when it comes to motivation and encouragement. The teacher in front of the classroom sets, to varying degrees, an example to follow. Definitely, the students have the possibility either to follow it or to reject it. Yet, in the majority of cases, the teacher is the one to motivate and inspire their students to study.

He / she should cultivate the desire to learn gradually diminishing his / her influence on the students' progress. Therefore, the teacher should encourage learner autonomy from the very beginning. The sooner the students are helped to realize the responsibility they have for their own formation as learners the better their learning will proceed. This implies that the teacher should use the techniques that will help attain his / her educational goals.

At the same time, one cannot deny the tremendous impact technology has on our lives. There are fewer and fewer people who have not been influenced, in a

way or another, by the technological progress. It has dramatically changed not only our way of living, but also our way of perceiving the reality, especially together with the appearance of internet. The virtual world has become appealing and, sometimes, people get lost in the labyrinth of web links losing the track of time. Young people, i.e. students, are particularly interested in surfing the net. One should not underestimate the power it has. However, its purpose is not solely to entertain. It abounds in information that can be used in different domains, including the process of learning. Thus, teachers should be encouraged to use technology tools both inside and outside the classroom to create more motivational learning environments. In addition, technology could serve the purpose of enhancing learner autonomy.

Definition of concepts the process of education is never-ending. Indeed, a person cannot stop at a certain stage of his / her life and say that his/ her education is complete. It is rather an on-going process that makes people strive for improvement and accomplishment, if they want to become acclaimed specialists. Thus, they should do most of the learning on their own and not wait for the teacher to lecture them. Yet, it is the teacher who should encourage them to rely on themselves more. That is why student-centred classrooms are the best environments to enhance responsibility and to encourage students take risks.

Thus, students are empowered, in a way, to make their own decisions concerning their learning. It is this power that makes some teachers reluctant to use the learner-centered approach in their teaching. Douglas Brown believes that teachers should not shy away from it. In his opinion, encouraging students to make their own choices (beginning even with the elementary level) helps "to give students a sense of 'ownership' of their learning and thereby add to their intrinsic motivation" . Definitely, the desire to learn should first of all come from within. Students should realize by themselves the importance of learning and be responsible for the choices they make. They should not constantly wait for the teacher's approval of what they do or say and be aware of the fact that "the most powerful rewards are those that are intrinsically motivated within the learner", as "the behavior stems from needs, wants, or desires within oneself, the behavior itself is self-rewarding; therefore, no externally administered reward is necessary" . In this case, the teacher is seen as facilitator of the learning process and not as instructor. Leo Jones's belief is that "being a teacher means helping people to learn - and, in a student centered class, the teacher is a member of the class as a participant in the learning process".

In this way, the teacher will enhance learner autonomy. Learner autonomy is above all responsibility that comes from the students' part who realize the importance of their own learning. Responsible learners are those who "accept the idea that their own efforts are crucial to progress learning, and behave accordingly". Being "commonly associated with the idea of freedom", learner autonomy should be fostered at all levels. Therefore, teachers "need to develop a sense of responsibility and also, encourage learners to take an active part in making decisions about their learning". At the same time, it should be emphasized that "in the traditional teaching-learning context, learner autonomy can only develop in an atmosphere in which both teachers and learners are sensitive to the mutual influences at play". It would be useful at this point to offer a definition of what teaching is. For example, in Jarvis's opinion "teaching is regarded as an intentional activity in which opportunities to learn are provided". In this way, the teacher governed by a concrete intention, i.e. objective, is to offer the students opportunities to learn. It implies that from the very beginning the teacher lives the student the possibility of choice. The process of teaching is also very complex in its essence. In Jarvis's opinion "teaching is changing; it is being forced to change by the dominant globalising forces of social change". It implies that teachers should be always aware of the latest changes and try to use them to get better results. The same thing can be referred to learner autonomy; a student is free to choose within the curriculum. This restraint is applied to both the teacher and the students. That is why the concept of learner autonomy always implies two factors: freedom, but, above all, responsibility. Students "consciously monitor their own progress, and make an effort to use available opportunities to their benefit".

At the same time, "loss of control, chaos and inefficient learning are threatening and presumed implications of learner autonomy". Yet, learner autonomy does not mean disorder. The teacher's presence is still crucial in facilitating the process of learning. What they should do is to take their role as facilitators seriously and not confound it with the one of controlling. Similarly, they should be open to the new changes in pedagogy and always adjust their goals to the new approaches answering the students' needs.

The scholar describes three stages. At the initial stage of autonomy, the emphasis is simply on raising the learner's awareness of the reasons behind the teacher's choice of goals, tasks, and materials. At the intermediary stage, the emphasis is on allowing the learner to choose from a range of options given by the teacher. Finally, at the advanced stage, the emphasis is on learner determination of his or her own goals, tasks, and materials. Undoubtedly, learner autonomy is

extremely complex in its essence and it can be “achieved only through continual struggle”. Thus, the teacher and students should be supportive all the way on this difficult path and always remember that hard work brings its own reward. Technology consumption – a new learning style? No one can deny the tremendous influence technology has nowadays. It has become essential in the way we watch films and listen to music, socialise and get informed. Thus, people have turned into huge technology consumers. This made educators consider using technology at the lessons in order to stimulate students’ intrinsic motivation. Students differ in the way they assimilate the new material better, they have their own style. As a matter of fact, the word itself has a very broad meaning; style is the particular way a person talks, behaves, dresses, etc. Learning style accordingly is the particular way a person prefers to study, a method that allows him / her to acquire the studied material easier. The first thing a teacher should do is to discover the students’ learning styles, which are “best thought of as a blend or profile that resides within every student”. The teacher should first determine what the most effective perceptive input is. In this way, the teacher is supposed to detect how the students mentally receive, perceive, process, understand, and internalize the new material. Thus, the teacher may notice that some students understand knowledge better if they are shown different visual aids, or if they are asked to perform an action related to the subject topic of the lesson. Taking into account the senses, students usually fall under four types of learners: visual learners, auditory learners, kinaesthetic learners and tactile learners. At the same time, there is another criterion in determining the student’s learning preferences. In this case, the teacher should consider how the student prefers to work (e.g. in group, individually) and learn (e.g. by thinking, by seeing the “whole” rather than in parts and vice versa).

As a result, there are: active learners, reflective learners, global learners and sequential learners. The Grasha-Riechmann model consists of six student learning styles, which in fact represent three pairs of dichotomies: competitive – collaborative, avoidant – participant, dependent – independent . It definitely depends on the way a student better acquires the new information, but it can only imply that the visual input of information prevails over the auditory. Thus, the visual aids will facilitate the process of learning but not necessary determine it. In general, a teacher should consider finding a balance among them so that every single student from the class acquires new knowledge. Technology could serve as a means that will help realize such a goal. The word technology is very often related to computer technology because “computers have so pervaded our daily

home and workplace contexts". Yet, technology comprises audio-tape players, video players, CD players, and, definitely, computers. The teachers started making use of technology ever since it appeared. For instance, audio-recordings are still used mostly for listening. The video recordings address visual and auditory learners. When technology became more accessible, teachers started encouraging students to make their own recordings or to produce their own films. In this way, students became actually involved in the process of learning, i.e. they were doing things. Thus, it may be appropriate to talk about the appearance of a new "techie" style. I would say that "techie" style would be a combination of more than one learning style as it addresses visual learners, as well as auditory learners or kinaesthetic learners. It includes any technology tool that helps in the reception and processing of the studied material. For example, students would assimilate better the material if it were presented in the form of a PPT. This kind of presentation addresses both auditory and visual styles, and the teacher could make it in such a way as to include other learning styles as well. However, there are teachers who believe that such presentation only boost students' laziness. They complain that students wait for these presentations not taking the trouble to study thoroughly the given topic. I would disagree here as, nowadays, our students are exposed to a variety of different information and they are at a loss. This PPT is to guide them and show what to pay attention to. The benefits of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) CALL is gaining more and more popularity together with the appearance of numerous computer softwares and hardwares meant to enhance the process of learning. It has become even difficult to keep pace with the latest technological inventions used for educational purposes.

Conclusions: Being technologically friendly, students should be encouraged to use technology for their academic progress. This would foster learner autonomy, and will make them sense the responsibility they have for their learning. Similarly, learner autonomy will enhance the security needed for risk taking, i.e. students will have to make their own decisions understanding the consequences they may lead to. Definitely, there are many challenges that both the teacher and students will have to deal with, but the determination to attain the set goals should prevail. Learner autonomy should be acquired step by step. Thus the teacher should be very patient and gradually diminish his / her presence in the students' learning process. Certainly, his / her impact is still significant as the teacher is the first to set an example to follow. He / She may influence the students' behaviour and inspire him to learn.

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